

Proposed Integrated Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana (Hadiprana Artwork)

Anugrah Fikriyanto¹, G.N. Sandhy Widyasthana²

^{1,2} School of Business Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: PT. Karya Seni Hadiprana (KSH) is a consultant and contractor company that provides artwork in architecture and interior industry. The company provides customize premium artwork products and services that have local content inspired from the rich of Indonesian culture. However they are having decreasing numbers of new customers and revenue streams due to global pandemic of COVID-19. Digitalization in architecture and interior industry also impact the PT KSH compare with other competitor who already utilized digital marketing strategy. The purpose of this study is to find out the reasons of the business issues, due to changing of customer behavior impact from Covid-19 and digitalization in architecture and interior industry. The research method uses qualitative descriptive methods. Qualitative descriptive methods are used to acquire primary data and make observation from in-depth interview with the company executives. The collection data is then to create internal and external analysis. The internal analysis is to gather the information about PT KSH internal conditions with Marketing Mix, Business Model Canvas and VRIO analysis, while the external analysis is used to evaluate the external factor of architecture and interior industry as well as customer behavior. Furthermore, after internal and external analysis was conducted, the researchers used SWOT analysis and find the weakness of the company, which lack of digital marketing strategy. Based on the analysis, researchers presented new integrated marketing strategy by optimizing digital marketing and improve marketing knowledge in order to increase awareness of products and services of PT Karya Seni Hadiprana.

KEYWORDS: Artwork, Architecture, Digital Marketing, Hadiprana, Marketing Mix, VRIO Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this information era, with the rapid growing of internet users, entrepreneurs running their business facing uncertain challenge or VUCA situation, which stands for for volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity- qualities that make situation or condition difficult to analyse, respond to or plan for. [1] Global Pandemic of Covid-19 is an example VUCA situation that becomes problem that business owners must tackle in recent years, especially in Indonesia. Across any industry, the most profound and long-lasting impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic might be in architecture and design. After all, the looming threat of outbreak has already prompted several design changes within built environments in 2020. [2] Trends in architecture and design stretch beyond the office setting to the home office. With more time at home, people are more sensitive to comfort and feel. [4] Align with the Forbes article in December 2021, artwork is one of architectural and interior elements that bring luxurious comfort to bring wellbeing senses. One of the companies in Jakarta, Indonesia, PT Karya Seni Hadiprana, or Hadiprana Artwork (PT KSH) which can provide artwork products and services for any architectural or interior space.

Changing of customer behavior is not threat for the business owners, especially for architecture and interior industry, but an opportunity to strengthen company digital marketing strategy and to optimize integrated marketing communication.[8] Using a digital marketing strategy can be a communication bridge between companies and the community to increase brand awareness, especially in big cities in Indonesia. Using a digital marketing strategy in the post-pandemic era can make it easier for newly established and well-established companies to reintroduce their products and services to the wider community. The objective of this research is to determine the internal and external conditions of PT Karya Seni Hadiprana, weakness of the company that cause of the company's decreasing revenue streams and new customers, and the implementation of the action plan.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Analyzing the company's internal condition needs to be done using the VRIO analysis framework, which includes analysis based on a resource-based view of both tangible and intangible resources. [9] By using VRIO analysis, which stands for "valuable, rare,

inimitable, and organized to capture," companies can determine strengths based on resources that have a competitive advantage. Furthermore, in order to complete the internal analysis of the company, it is necessary to understand the marketing strategy with the marketing mix, namely determining the company's positioning through product, price, place, and promotion. [6] Using customer analysis is also important to find out the customer's point of view, especially in terms of understanding related industries. [5] From a broader perspective, PESTEL analysis considers the impact of the company's industry's external environment on the continuity of its business in related industries. [9] From the standpoint of the external environment, it is also necessary to analyze which competitors are directly in the same industry and understand each competitor's strengths and weaknesses. [5] By combining internal and external conditions, a SWOT analysis can be used to determine the company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. [7] Digital marketing is a solution because it allows businesses to connect with customers electronically through interactive technologies such as emails, websites, online forums, mobile communication, and so on. [6] Through a continuous dialogue that includes expressing interest, requesting products and services, suggesting improvements, and providing feedback, digital marketing can help the company's business become more customer-oriented. [3]

3. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative and descriptive methodologies were utilized in this research. To better understand the business process of the company, the qualitative research method gathers interpretation. Primary data and secondary data are the two categories of data used in this study. The artwork director, principle designer, and project coordinator were the executives who participated in in-depth interviews that provided the core data for this study. Primary data was also gathered through a questionnaire survey of the company's prospective clients. A firm internal report, publications, magazines, newspaper articles, and other media sources were used to collect secondary data for this study. The company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats will be identified through a SWOT analysis of all the data. Each framework's analysis findings will. To identify the company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, all of the data will be subjected to a SWOT analysis. Each framework's analysis findings will be collected. The strategy will be decided using digital marketing and marketing mix 7P's.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. SWOT

1) Internal Analysis: Strength and Weakness

Strength of PT Karya Seni Hadiprana

- PT Karya Seni Hadiprana is one stop solution for artwork products and services that offers various type of artwork ranging from wall artwork to the monumental landscape artwork.
- PT Karya Seni Hadiprana offers design based on local content and inspired from Indonesian local culture
- PT Karya Seni Hadiprana have curated suppliers that can produce any materials artwork to support architecture and interior Industry
- PT Karya Seni Hadiprana have internal workshop with internal artisan who have specialized skilled from wood carving, special paint finishing and sculpture building
- The company have standard certification in form of ISO 9001 for decades to make sure the products and quality service to the customers.

Weakness of PT Karya Seni Hadiprana

- The company lacks of marketing channels and depends on Hadiprana group channels to get potential customers
- PT Karya Seni Hadiprana production capacity is not big enough to supply ready stock items to the retail channels, both online and offline.

2) External Analysis: Opportunities and Threats Opportunities

for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana

- Government support in architectural and interior industry in Indonesian Vision of National Architecture Development until 2025 to support local architecture
- Government regulation for construction industry to have local content in form of TKDN 25%

- Increase demand of architecture and interior design that show from increase GDP in Creative Economy in subsector of Architecture, Interior and Craft Industry
- Local Architecture Design bring positive impact due to Pandemic Covid-19, with Interior Decoration will increase immune [3]

Threats for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana

- The company will face new entrant's competitor due to digitalization era, customers shift to purchase products or services online.
- Direct competitor possesses digital marketing strategy with utilizing social media marketing that focus to offer artwork products and services.

B. Digital Marketing Strategy for PT. Karya Seni Hadiprana

Based on initial business issues, PT Karya Seni Hadiprana revenue streams and the number of new customers are decreasing. Conducting SWOT analysis from internal and external analysis there are several potential problems occurred, especially from the marketing aspects. From SWOT analysis, there is several aspects in terms in marketing communication that leads to business issues. Therefore to for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana can solve the business issues and become more customers centric, the proposed digital marketing strategy are as below:

1) Product & Pricing

- To solve the business issues and increasing the revenue, the company need to add more solution integrates to the digital marketing strategy, which is developing the digital product. As for business solution to PT Karya Seni Hadiprana, should also separate their company websites and social media with Hadiprana Design in order to offer digital products in the dedicated website. The business solution for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana product section is to use a digital marketing mix approach, namely co-creation and collaboration.
- The pricing solution for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana is premium pricing without displaying the price for the product and services. Customers can enquire the price if they interested to buy the products that utilizing luxury perceived products in company websites and social media.

2) Place

- Based on the previous chapter's SWOT analysis, PT Karya Seni Hadiprana identified a lack of online channels in the context of digital marketing. PT Karya Seni Hadiprana should create not only an online company website but also an online multichannel, such as social media channels and online retail channels.

3) Promotion

- There are business issues in promotion section, such as social media channels not fully optimized to get new customers, the company also not utilizing SEO and social media ads, also it relied on family relation. Besides using SEO, PT Karya Seni Hadiprana should use paid advertisements on social media to raise awareness. PT Karya Seni Hadiprana should create content such as a photo of all of its artwork product types. The company can include the phone number, What Sapp business contact information, warehouse address, and company website on the social media homepage. PT Karya Seni Hadiprana can maintain the loyalty in long-term relationship by re-call the customers by phone, social media messaging, or email messaging to ask whether there is a product or services to be requested.

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6) People

- Training Existing PT KSH Team to do Marketing Activities,
- Hire Marketing Manager,
- Partnership with Customer as Online PR,

- Create Marketing Division of PT Karya Seni Hadiprana, and
- Create Knowledge Management System about Marketing for Every Division.. 7) Physical Evident & Process
- Customers seek assurance that the service will be satisfactory because it is intangible. For PT Karya Seni Hadiprana business solution, physical evidence is website of the company, and with the credentials, such as clients and project portfolio that company has been built. Customers need transparent information about the progress of product and services they already purchase.

4. CONCLUSION

From research with PT. KSH, the examination of internal and external analysis of the company has been done. In Marketing Mix analysis, in terms of products, PT KSH focusing it to provide artwork products and services. In terms of price, PT KSH utilize premium pricing strategy due to the PT KSH brand positioning, which is provide premium artwork with unique local content for customers. In terms of place, PT KSH utilize multiple channels, from Hadiprana brand group website and social media and distribute the ready stock product to their related group retail store, Mitra Hadiprana (House of Hadiprana). In terms of promotion, PT KSH utilizes traditional channels, word of mouth from the family relation besides using Hadiprana Group social media and website. In competitor analysis PT KSH has strong direct competitors with more focused and well established digital marketing strategy, in form of social media and company websites. Based on internal report, PT KSH should focus more to get design and procure contract to leverage the revenue streams and cover the cost structure with available resources.

According to marketing perspectives, the root causes of PT. KSH's increased brand awareness of artwork products and services are in product, price, promotion, and people. PT KSH reports a lack of ready-to-ship items and that customers are having difficulty finding the products online. Pricing-wise, PT KSH's pricing is not competitive when compared to new entrants who offer substitute products at a lower cost. PT. Karya Seni does not yet have a proper marketing program or social media marketing strategy. On the human resources front, PT. KSH does not yet have the professional resources and proper knowledge management in place to support and optimize its marketing strategy.

In order to solve the main problem based on the SWOT analysis of PT. KSH, the researcher proposed a marketing remix strategy using the 7Ps and 5As of Kotler's Customer Path to map the customer experience and gave recommendations for solving business issues to increase brand awareness of artwork, products, and services for PT. KSH. The solution then categorized based on the timeline category, to scale the priority for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana. To implement the solution there are two categories, which are:

- 1) Short-term implementation
 - Create Marketing Content Strategy Creation to integrate offline and online marketing strategy
 - Create WhatsApp Business for PT Karya Seni Hadiprana for customer services
 - Create Facebook and Instagram Company Page and Ads
 - .Create LinkedIn Company Page and Ads to increase awareness for corporate clients segments
 - Create Company Websites and Integrate with Hadiprana Design Website to do cross selling strategy □ Utilizing Direct Email Marketing with Newsletter to increase call to action to leads sales
- 2) Long-term implementation
 - Create Marketing Divisions to handle all marketing strategy
 - Create Knowledge Management Systems for Marketing Integration
 - Develop Ready stock products & Partnership with Luxury Online Retailers

PT KSH prioritizes Social media marketing in short term plan, due to the action more feasible related to internal resources and budget. PT KSH social Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn as the social network platforms. PT KSH also implemented content strategy marketing plan and advertisement combined for social media marketing. The strategy for advertisement placement also important due to according to customer analysis before most of the existing customers have low rate purchasing in Q2 and Q4, so the solution is boosted with ads. PT KSH also implemented Search Engine Optimization in short-term business solution to reach more local based awareness, with selection of key phrases. Company websites utilize at the end of Q2 and early Q3 due to need development to build proper website, by collecting appropriate project portfolio. PT KSH also utilizes direct email marketing to

engage customers through newsletter. –Marketing division and Marketing Manager is not prioritize for the company but it necessary when marketing activities grow larger, for example website launching and partnership with online retailers. Distribute the product to the online retailers is PT KSH long-term marketing solution, due to need products and services preparation and due diligent to do partnership

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